

A Study on Thermal Performance of Bio-Convective MHD Casson Amalgam Nanofluid Flow Across an Extending Surface

Krishnan Sivasankari¹, Dr. V. Sugunamma^{2*}

¹ *Research Scholar, Department of Mathematics, Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati -517502, Andhra Pradesh, India.*

² *Professor, Department of Mathematics, Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati- 517502, Andhra Pradesh, India.*

Abstract:

The thermal radiation response of MHD Casson amalgam nanofluid flow due to bio-convection and chemical effects across an extending surface is focused along with Joule heating effects in the present manuscript. To sort out the boundary value problems, Runge Kutta, together with a shooting strategy, opted for. The physical perceptions are illuminated by running reckoning code in MATLAB (Matrix Laboratory) software using worthy boundary conditions. For different fluid variables like Casson fluid variable β , Eckert number Ec , thermal radiation R_d , magnetic parameter M , mixed convection parameter λ , Buoyancy ratio parameter N_r , Brownian motion parameter N_b , thermophoresis parameter N_t , bio-convection Rayleigh parameter N_c , aggregated outcomes on velocity, concentration, temperature and motile microorganisms are evaluated through graphs and tables. The immense Casson fluid value lowers the fluid's velocity result, lessening the of the boundary surface's impelling force. The fluid's temperature is raised by raising the Casson fluid variable and thermal radiation, which develops effective thermal diffusivity. Due to innumerable applications of amalgam nanofluids in industrial and engineering fields, the interest in studying the flow of boundary layer on hybrid nanofluids across an expanding sheet aroused. By executing similitude variables, the flow equations in problem formulation are transfigured to ordinary differential equations using Runge-Kutta technique. The controls of different physical limits on skin friction, Nusselt number are executed, and the procured results are applied for abundant high-tech practices of radiators functioning.

Keywords: Casson amalgam nanofluid, bio-convection, chemical effects, RK (Runge Kutta) technique.

1.Introduction:

In recent days, the interesting topic of the researchers includes the study of heat transfer of nanofluid particles across expanding surface because of their countless uses over engineering and industry. Nanoparticles and sample fluids like water, ethylene glycols and so on are mixed to obtain the nanofluid. It has ability to strengthen the fluid's transcalency, heat carrier and is utilized by industries for power generation, extrusion, metal spinning, cooling process etc. Gao et al. ^[1] studied about the changes caused due to nanofluid' glide between aligned plates build with collocation approach. Cui et al. ^[2] focused on viscous fluid's flow vigor transmission across expanding sheet by magnetic and thermal reaction. Ali et al. ^[3] investigated the bio-convective nanofluid heat transfer along with Cattaneo Christov using FEM (Finite Element Method) method.

Hybrid nanofluids are formed using monofluid to the many nanofluids. Casson hybrid nanofluid is a liquid which has Pseudo plastic flow behavior containing nought shearness, with boundless viscosity and vice versa. Fruit juices, Fruit jam, chocolate etc are some exemplars of Casson fluid. One of the best error less model to explore fluid dynamics in a forceful malleable viscidness is Casson fluid prototype. A bioreactor is one such prototype in which Coriolis force is observed along a non-uniform sheet due to the flow of Casson fluid containing microorganisms. Abayomis oke et al. ^[4] observed the influence in attributes of Casson fluid due to Coriolis force along non-uniform sheet. Sneha Gajbhiye et al. ^[5] examined the analytical treatment between the parallel plates on Casson fluid including the chemical reaction and hall effect. Kumar R.V.S. et al. ^[6] studied about the modeling method on Casson fluid across an expanding surface due to Lorentz forces.

Due to the swimming of microorganisms, a pattern formed resulting in convective motions i.e., heat transfer which is referred as Bio-convection and the movement of microorganism depends on the mass distribution of bio-convection. This Bio-convection phenomenon can be observed in enormous applications like medicament, solar cell equipment, biosensors, biomedicine etc. In recent times, the research based on bio-convection hybrid nanofluid flow across stretching sheet has become an exciting topic. Surya Kanta Mondal et al. ^[7] computationally analyzed the heat exchange properties of nanofluids across expanding surface that contains microorganisms. Waqas et al. ^[8] studied the Reiner Philipp oof's Marangoni-Bio-convectonal flow having irregular thermal source/sink with microorganisms. Ahmad Sohail et al. ^[9] observed bio-convection, resulting heat transfer in nanofluid containing microorganisms inside a penetrable medium. Aziz Ullah Awan et al. ^[10] examined the influence on Williamson nanofluid with heat transfer, chemical effects on expanding sheet. Muhammad Jawad et al. ^[11] studied the

reaction of mass distribution, thermal variations on nanofluid caused by the movement of microorganisms along an expanding surface. Arun et al. ^[12] examined about bio-radiative thermal transmission over an expanding/diminishing upright surface.

The incompressible flow of amalgam nanofluid on boundary surface have innumerable applications in industrial and engineering fields like porous rocks, polymer blends, extrusion process, production of glass-fibre etc. Due to this, it became an arousing topic for researcher to focus the flow of boundary layer on hybrid nanofluids across an expanding surface. Gowda et al. ^[13] examined about flow of boundary layer on nanofluid based on Marangoni method. Lund et al. ^[14] studied the micropolar nanofluid's impact across expanding/contracting sheet with boundary condition.

The chemical reaction plays an important role in bio-convection effects because of the motion of microorganisms on hybrid nanofluid due to the presence of boundary layer containing nanoparticles. Muhammad Imran Asjad et al. ^[15] investigated the influence of MHD nanofluid flow including bio-radiation, chemical response across an permeable surface. Damala Chennakesavaiah et al. ^[16] studied the influence on flow of Casson amalgam nanofluid due to chemical reaction over a pentrable expanding surface having suction/injection. Rashid Pourrajab et al. ^[17] examined the impact of nanofluid due to motion of microorganisms along an expanding sheet. Sandhya et al. ^[18] examined about the effect due to viscous scattering on Casson fluid across a stretching surface.

In engineering, the thermal radiation heat transfer flow plays a prominent role in different techniques such as designing the nuclear power plants, propulsion engines, gas turbines etc. Khalid Abdul Khaliq M. Alharbi et al. ^[19] investigated on micropolar fluid bio-convection along a stretching sheet. Pooja Humane et al. ^[20] discussed about the magnetic, chemical influences on Casson amalgam nanofluid. Adnan Asghar et al. ^[21] examined the magnetic influences on 3D (Three dimensional) amalgam nanofluid along with thermal radiation. Hasona et al. ^[22] discussed about heat exchange attributes on peristaltic flow of nanofluids with the application of radiotherapy of cancer. Mohamad Nizam Othman et al. ^[23] investigated on MHD nanofluid along contracting sheet. Muhammad Jawad et al. ^[24] examined about bio-convection influence of nanofluid across a stretching surface including the motion of microorganisms in the presence of heat and mass transmission. Dharmendra Reddy Yanala et al. ^[25] studied the influence of Casson amalgam nanofluid because of thermal transmission across an expanding Riga plate including thermal expansion. Yousef et al. ^[26] examined the influence on Williamson Casson amalgam nanofluid flow due to thermal expansion, mass transmission along an expanding surface. Syed Asif Ali Shah et al. ^[27] focused the impact on non-Newtonian fluid including bio-convection, chemical reaction across enlarging sheet.

The literature survey that is mentioned above proves that few studies carried out on bio-convective Casson hybrid nanofluid flow including chemical reaction. The existing paper analyzes the thermal performance of bio-convection effects on flow of MHD Casson amalgam nanofluid across an enlarging surface. Mathematically, model is reduced by the execution of similitude variables, the flow equations in problem formulation are transfigured to ordinary differential equations and the reduced governing equations are executed using MATLAB software with Runge-Kutta technique. The physical perceptions on concentration, motile microbes, temperature and velocity, are evaluated with the help of graphs and tables, and the results are compared among basefluid and hybrid nanofluid flow. The existing learning builds the objective of how far the thermal transmission rate can be stimulated.

2. Methodology:

Considered 2D unsteady Casson amalgam nanofluid flow over an expanding surface with gyrotactic motile microorganisms. The fluid is assumed to flow at $y > 0$ and the coordinates are taken as (x, y) . An angle α is made by magnetic field along x -axis normal to the fluid flow. Over x -axis, the extending surface has the velocity $u_w(x) = ax$ which is represented in the figure given below.

Fig1: Fluid flow Geometry

The corresponding equations of Casson amalgam nanofluid are :

$$\text{Continuity Equation} \quad : \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = 0 \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Momentum Equation} \quad : \quad v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \vartheta_{hnf} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\sigma_{hnf}}{\rho_{hnf}} B_0^2 u \sin^2 \alpha + \frac{1}{\rho_{hnf}} [g(T - T_\infty) \rho_f \beta (1 - c_\infty) + g(c_\infty - c)(\rho_f + \rho_p) - (\rho_m - \rho_p)(N_\infty - N)g\gamma] \tag{2}$$

$$\text{Energy Equation} \quad : \quad v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = \alpha_{hnf} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \tau \left[\left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)^2 \frac{DT}{T_\infty} + \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} D_B \frac{\partial c}{\partial y} - \frac{1}{\rho_{cp}} \frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} + \frac{\sigma_{hnf}}{(\rho_{cp})_{hnf}} B_0^2 u^2 \right] \tag{3}$$

$$\text{Concentration Equation} \quad : \quad v \frac{\partial c}{\partial y} + u \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial y^2} D_B \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \frac{DT}{T_\infty} + k_r (c_\infty - c) \tag{4}$$

$$\text{Motile Microorganism Equation} \quad : \quad v \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} + u \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} = D_m \frac{\partial^2 N}{\partial y^2} + \frac{b\omega_c}{(c_\infty - c)} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(N \frac{\partial c}{\partial y} \right) \tag{5}$$

The terms contained in the above equations are presented in nomenclature. The boundary conditions are:

$$\text{When } y=0, \quad v = 0, \quad u_w = u = ax, \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = -(T_w - T) \frac{h}{k_{hnf}}, \quad c_w = c, \quad N_w = N \tag{6}$$

$$\text{When } y \rightarrow \infty, \quad c_\infty = c, \quad u=0, \quad T_\infty = T, \quad N_\infty = N \tag{7}$$

The corresponding PDEs are changed to ODEs by using the similarity relations mentioned below:

$$\eta = \sqrt{\frac{a}{\vartheta_f}} y, \quad \theta(\eta) = \frac{(T-T_\infty)}{(T_w-T_\infty)}, \quad \phi(\eta) = \frac{(c_\infty-c)}{(c_\infty-c_w)}, \quad \chi(\eta) = \frac{(N-N_\infty)}{(N_w-N_\infty)}, \quad u = ax f', \quad v = -\sqrt{a\vartheta_f} f \tag{8}$$

The transformed equations are as follows:

$$f''' \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 f'^2) - B_2 f' M \sin^2 \alpha + B_1 (ff'' - f'^2) + B_2 (\theta - Nr\phi + Nc\chi)\lambda = 0 \tag{9}$$

$$\frac{1}{PrB_3} \left[\frac{4}{3} Rd + \frac{1}{B_4} \right] \theta'' + f\theta' + Nb\theta'\phi' + Nt\theta'^2 + \frac{EcMf'^2}{B_3B_5} = 0 \tag{10}$$

$$\phi'' + fLe\phi' + \frac{Nt}{Nb}\theta'' - \gamma\phi = 0 \tag{11}$$

$$\chi'' + fLb\chi' - (\chi'\phi' + (\omega + \chi)\phi'')Pe = 0 \tag{12}$$

The compatible boundary conditions are

$$\text{When } \eta \rightarrow 0, \quad f = 0, \quad f' = 0, \quad \theta' = B_4 B_i (\theta - 1), \quad \phi = 0, \quad \chi = 1 \tag{13}$$

$$\text{When } \eta \rightarrow \infty, \quad f' = 0, \quad \theta \rightarrow 0, \quad \phi \rightarrow 0, \quad \chi \rightarrow 0 \tag{14}$$

Here $M = \frac{\sigma_f B_0^2}{\rho_f a}$ is magnetic parameter, $Nr = \frac{(\rho_p + \rho_f)(c_w - c_\infty)}{\rho_f \beta (1 - c_\infty)(T_w - T_\infty)}$ is Buoyancy ratio parameter, $Nt = \frac{(T_w - T_\infty)\tau DT}{\vartheta_f T_\infty}$ is thermophoresis, $Bi = \frac{h}{\vartheta_f} \sqrt{\frac{\vartheta_f}{a}}$ is thermal Biot number, $Nc = \frac{\gamma^*(\rho_m - \rho_f)(N_w - N_\infty)}{\rho_f \beta (c_\infty - 1)(T_w - T_\infty)}$ is Rayleigh number of bio-convection, $Rd = \frac{4\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{K^* K_f}$ is radiation parameter, $Ec = \frac{u_w^2}{c_{p_f}(T_w - T_\infty)}$ is Eckert number, $Nb = \frac{\tau D_B (c_w - c_\infty)}{\vartheta_f}$ is Brownian motion parameter, $\lambda = \frac{(1 - c_\infty)\beta g(T_w - T_\infty)}{a^2 x}$ is mixed convection parameter, $Le = \frac{\vartheta_f}{D_B}$ is Lewis number, $\gamma = \frac{k\gamma}{a} Le$ is Chemical reaction parameter, $Lb = \frac{\vartheta_f}{D_m}$ is bio-convection Lewis number, $W = \frac{N_\infty}{(N_w - N_\infty)}$ is bio-convection constant, $Pr = \frac{\vartheta_f (\rho_{cp})_f}{K_f}$ is Prandtl number, $Pe = \frac{b\omega_c}{D_m}$ is Peclet number.

Table I and Table II shows the attributes of thermo-physical properties

TableI. Thermal attributes of amalgam nanofluid

Attributes	Nanofluid	Amalgam Nanofluid
Viscosity	$\mu_{nf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1-\phi)^{2.5}}$	$\mu_{hnf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1-\phi_1)^{2.5}(1-\phi_2)^{2.5}}$
Density	$\rho_{nf} = (\phi \left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f}\right) + (1 - \phi))\rho_f$	$\rho_{hnf} = (1 - \phi_2)(\phi_1 \left(\frac{\rho_{s1}}{\rho_f}\right) + (1 - \phi_1)\rho_f)$
Heat capacity	$(\rho c_p)_{nf} = \left((1 - \phi) + \phi \left(\frac{(\rho c_p)_s}{(\rho c_p)_f}\right) \right) (\rho c_p)_f$	$(\rho c_p)_f = (1 - \phi_2) \left(\phi_1 \left(\frac{\rho_{s1}}{\rho_f}\right) + (1 - \phi_1) \right) \rho_f$
Thermal conductivity	$\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} = \frac{-(m-1)\phi(k_f-k_s)+k_s+(m-1)k_f}{\phi(k_f-k_s)+k_s+(m-1)k_f}$	$\frac{k_{hnf}}{k_{bf}} = \frac{k_{s2}+(m-1)k_{bf}-(m-1)\phi_2(k_{bf}-k_{s2})}{k_{s2}+(m-1)k_{bf}+\phi_2(k_{bf}-k_{s2})}$ Where, $\frac{k_{bf}}{k_f} = \frac{k_{s1}+(m-1)k_f-(m-1)\phi_1(k_f-k_{s1})}{k_{s1}+(m-1)k_f+\phi_1(k_f-k_{s1})}$
Electrical conductivity	$\frac{\sigma_{nf}}{\sigma_f} = 1 + \frac{3\left(\frac{\sigma_s}{\sigma_f}-1\right)\phi}{2+\left(\frac{\sigma_s}{\sigma_f}\right)-\left(\frac{\sigma_s}{\sigma_f}-1\right)\phi}$	$\frac{\sigma_{hnf}}{\sigma_{bf}} = \frac{\sigma_{s2}+2\sigma_{bf}-2\phi_2(\sigma_{bf}-\sigma_{s2})}{\sigma_{s2}+2\sigma_{bf}+\phi_2(\sigma_{bf}-\sigma_{s2})}$ Where, $\frac{\sigma_{bf}}{\sigma_f} = \frac{\sigma_{s1}+2\sigma_f-2\phi_1(\sigma_f-\sigma_{s1})}{\sigma_{s1}+2\sigma_f+\phi_1(\sigma_f-\sigma_{s1})}$

TableII. Thermal attributes of nanofluids and water

Nano/Base fluids	(Copper) Cu	(Titanium dioxide) TiO ₂	(water) H ₂ O
ρ (kg.m ⁻³)	8933	4250	997.1
c_p (J.kg ⁻¹ .k ⁻¹)	385	686.2	4179
k (W.m ⁻¹ .k ⁻¹)	401	8.9538	0.613
σ (Ω ⁻¹ .m ⁻¹)	59.6	0.125	5.5

And

$$B_1 = \left[\left((1 - \phi_1) + \phi_1 \frac{\rho_{s1}}{\rho_f} \right) (1 - \phi_2) + \frac{\rho_{s2}}{\rho_f} \phi_2 \right] (1 - \phi_2)^{2.5} (1 - \phi_1)^{2.5} \tag{15}$$

$$B_2 = (1 - \phi_2)^{2.5} (1 - \phi_1)^{2.5} \tag{16}$$

$$B_3 = \left((1 - \phi_1) + \phi_1 \frac{(\rho c_p)_{s1}}{(\rho c_p)_f} \right) (1 - \phi_2) + \frac{(\rho c_p)_{s2}}{(\rho c_p)_f} \phi_2 \tag{17}$$

$$B_4 = \frac{k_{s2}+(m-1)k_{bf}+\phi_2(k_{bf}-k_{s2})}{k_{s2}+(m-1)k_{bf}-(m-1)\phi_2(k_{bf}-k_{s2})} \cdot \frac{k_{s1}+(m-1)k_f+\phi_1(k_f-k_{s1})}{k_{s1}+(m-1)k_f-(m-1)\phi_1(k_f-k_{s1})} \tag{18}$$

$$B_5 = \frac{\sigma_{s2}+2\sigma_{bf}+\phi_2(\sigma_{bf}-\sigma_{s2})}{\sigma_{s2}+2\sigma_{bf}-2\phi_2(\sigma_{bf}-\sigma_{s2})} \frac{\sigma_{s1}+2\sigma_f+\phi_1(\sigma_f-\sigma_{s1})}{\sigma_{s1}+2\sigma_f-2\phi_1(\sigma_f-\sigma_{s1})} \tag{19}$$

The physical quantities are defined as follows:

$$C_{fx} = \frac{\tau_w}{\rho_f u_w^2}, Nu_x = \frac{x q_w^*}{k_f (\tau_w - \tau_\infty)} \tag{20}$$

The heat flux, Shear stress on the boundary are $\tau_w = \mu_{hnf} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) \left(\frac{A}{c} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{A}{2c^3} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^3 \right)$ and $q_w^* = -k_{hnf} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}$ respectively.

Using similarity transformations equations (20) give

$$C_{fx} = \frac{1}{B_2} Re_x^{-0.5} f''(0) \tag{21}$$

$$Nu_x = \frac{k_{hnf}}{k_f} Re_x^{-0.5} \theta'(0), \text{ where } Re_x = \frac{u w_x}{\nu_f} \text{ is Reynolds number} \tag{22}$$

3. Results and Discussion:

The mathematical solutions of governing parameters of flow of the fluids are examined by adopting MATLAB software with Runge-Kutta and shooting technique and are presented with the help of graphs and tables. The impact of various affecting physical perceptions on concentration, motile microbes, temperature and velocity are executed by assigning certain values to them. Table III describes the compatibility with the previous work of Ali et al [27] and Syed Asif Ali Shah et al [28]. Table IV describes the algebraic values of Nusselt number, skin friction among base, amalgam nanofluid.

Table III. Collated outcomes for M values with Ali et al[27] and Syed Asif Ali Shah et at [28]

M	Ali et al[27]	Syed Asif Ali Shah et at [28]	Present outcomes
0.2	1.0954458	1.09544603	1.09544615
0.5	1.2247446	1.22474492	1.22474498
1.0	1.4142132	1.41421356	1.41421363
1.2	1.4832393	1.48323970	1.48323993
1.5	1.5811384	1.58113883	1.58113892
2.0	1.7320504	1.73205081	1.73205095

Table IV. Algebraic values of C_{fx} and N_{hx} of base and amalgam nanofluid for distinct physical limits.

M	β	Rd	Nt	Nb	Bi	Ec	α	Skinfriction TiO ₂ /water	Skinfriction Cu+TiO ₂ /water	NusseltNumber TiO ₂ /water	NusseltNumber Cu+TiO ₂ /water
3.0	0.5	2.0	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	45	-0.671216	-0.680463	0.047343	0.050528
4.0								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
5.0								-0.901311	-0.926324	0.009811	0.007828
								-0.975580	-0.997418	0.29044	0.031896
								-1.129508	-1.154981	0.035361	0.038453
								-1.199489	-1.226646	0.037571	0.040774
								-0.796267	-0.814057	0.016329	0.015655
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.793970	-0.811740	0.032339	0.035537
								-0.792770	-0.810451	0.024142	0.026763
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.795774	-0.813490	0.011624	0.014133
	2.0	3.0	0.2	0.2	0.2	45	45	-0.789921	-0.807375	0.027978	0.030748
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.797803	-0.815692	0.007654	0.009976
								-0.793629	-0.811297	0.010436	0.011761
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794568	-0.812289	0.024107	0.027825
								-0.776217	-0.793145	0.087025	0.090654
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.812992	-0.831592	0.052693	0.051479
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.982032	-1.012717	0.028027	0.030741
								-1.139575	-1.180657	0.034154	0.037084
	3.0	4.0	0.2	0.2	0.2	45	45	-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
	4.0	2.0	0.3	0.2	0.1	45	45	-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
	4.0	3.0	0.4	0.3	0.2	45	45	-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
	4.0	4.0	0.4	0.4	0.3	45	45	-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745
								-0.794158	-0.811850	0.018162	0.020745

Fig 2(a) depicts the influence of Casson fluid parameter β on velocity contour such that the velocity profile declines by increasing β value. Concluded that higher quantity of Casson fluid parameter vanish thermal, momentum thickness of boundary layer, and result in high viscous force on fluid flow and hence velocity profile decreases. Fig 2(b) – 2(f) depict the impact of mixed convection parameter λ , angle of inclination α , and bio-convection Rayleigh number Nc , magnetic parameter M and buoyancy ratio parameter Nr on velocity profile for both the fluid flow and hence raising these parameters, the velocity contour decreases with the effect of Lorentz force.

The temperature profile is raised with increases in Casson fluid parameter and thermal conduction which develops the high thermal diffusivity and are displayed in fig 3(a) and 3(b). Fig 3(c) to 3(f) describe that increasing values of Ekert number Ec , parameter of thermophoresis Nt , Brownian motion parameter Nb and thermal Biot number Bi , temperature profile increases. This achieves with higher Brownian motion parameter resulting in raising kinetic energy of motion of fluid flow particles. Also, the larger the Biot number, the smaller boundary layer thickness.

The impact of magnetic parameter, Lewis number, thermophoresis parameter of both fluids on concentration profile are exhibited in fig 4(a), 4(b) and 4(c). It proves that concentration profile raises with higher quantity of magnetic parameter M , thermophoresis parameter Nt and exhibits opposite behavior for Lewis number Le values. Increasing the Brownian motion parameter Nb , chemical reaction parameter γ , concentration profile decreases which are shown in fig 4(d) and 4(e). Raising the thermophoresis parameter Nt values uplift the fluid particles which enhances the kinetic energy and develops the boundary layer. Also increasing the Nb values affect the acceleration of fluid flow particles result in rapid movement of fluid particles. The behavior of motile microorganisms with the effect of modifying the Peclet number Pe , Bio-convection Lewis number Lb and Bio-convection constant ω are illustrated in fig 4(f)-4(g), where microbe profile decreases with increase in Pecelt number Pe , Bio-convection Lewis number Lb and Bio-convection constant ω values.

Figure 2: Velocity profile for M , β , λ , α , Nr and Nc

Figure 3: Temperature profile for β , Rd , Ec , Nt , Nb and Bi

Figure 4(a) Deviations of ϕ with M

Figure 4(b) Deviations of ϕ with Le

Figure 4(c) Deviations of ϕ with Nt

Figure 4(d) Deviations of ϕ with Nb

Figure 4(e) Deviations of ϕ with γ

Figure 4(f) Deviations of χ with Lb

Figure 4: Concentration profile for M, Le, Nt, Nb, γ and Motile microorganism profile for Lb, Pe, ω

4. Conclusions:

The thermal performance of bio-convective Casson amalgam nanofluid across an expanding surface has been evaluated. In this paper, by executing similitude variables, the influence of chemical reaction, thermal radiation, Casson amalgam fluids' temperature, motile microorganisms, velocity, and contour of concentration are estimated. Observations are discussed below.

- For the immense quantity of Casson fluid variable, inclination angle, magnetic variable and bio-convection Rayleigh number, the velocity contour decreases.
- The temperature contour gets reduced by raising Casson fluid variable, Eckert number and has positive behavior for thermophoresis, thermal radiation variables. The temperature profile of hybrid nanofluids are highly remarkable compared to nanofluids.
- Uplifting the values of magnetic and thermophoresis variables, the concentration contour increases for both the fluids.
- The microorganisms contour of both fluids have negative effect for higher quantities of Peclet, bio-convection number.
- The Skin friction coefficient has negative behavior for large numbers of inclination angle, thermophoresis parameter and similar for higher quantity of Casson fluid parameter, Brownian motion parameter, Biot number.
- The Nusselt number raises with immense quantity of Casson fluid parameter, Biot number and decreases for Magnetic parameter, inclination angle, thermophoresis parameter, Brownian motion parameter values.

This current analysis of bio-convective thermal performance across a stretching sheet encourages the interest in researchers for its enormous applications in industrial, medical and engineering fields. The research can be extended with different non-Newtonian fluid like Williamson nanofluid, amalgam nanofluids and by varying the dimensions of the fluid flow.

References:

1. Gao, F.; Yu, D.; Sheng, Q. Analytical treatment of unsteady fluid flow of nonhomogeneous nanofluids among two infinite parallel surfaces: Collocation method-based study, *Mathematics* 2022, 10(9), 1-13, <https://doi.org/10.3390/math10091556>.
2. Cui, J.; Razzaq, R.; Farooq, U.; Khan, W.A.; Farooq, F.B.; Muhammad, T. Impact of non-similar modeling for forced convection analysis of nano-fluid flow over stretching sheet with chemical reaction and heat generation, *Alexandria Engineering Journal* 2022, 61(6), 4253–426, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2021.09.045>.
3. Ali, L.; Ali, B.; Ghori, M.B. Melting effect on Cattaneo Christov and thermal radiation features for aligned MHD nanofluid flow comprising microorganisms to leading edge: FEM approach, *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, 2022, 109(1), 260–269, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.camwa.2022.01.009>.
4. Abayomi S.Oke, Winifred N. Mutuku, Mark Klmathi and Issac L. Animasaun, Insight into the dynamics of Non-Newtonian Casson fluid over a rotating non-uniform surface subject to Coriolis force, *Non-linear Engineering*, 2022, 9(1), 398-411, <https://doi.org/10.1515/nleng-2020-0025>.
5. Sneha Gajbhiye, Arundhati Warke and Katta Ramesh, Analysis of energy and momentum transport for Casson nanofluid in a microchannel with radiation and chemical reaction effects, *Waves in random and complex media*, 2022, 32(4), 1745-1768, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17455030.2022.2097749>.
6. Kumar, R.S.V.; Dhananjaya, P.G.; Kumar, R.N.; Gowda, R.J.P.; Prasannakumara, Modeling and theoretical investigation on Casson nanofluid flow over a curved stretching surface with the influence of magnetic field and chemical reaction. *International journal for computational methods in engineering science and mechanics* 2022, 23(1), 12–19, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15502287.2021.1900451>.

7. Surya Kanta Mondal and Dulal Pal, Computational analysis of bio-convective flow of nanofluid containing gyrotactic microorganisms over a nonlinear stretching sheet with variable viscosity using HAM, *Journal of Computational Design and Engineering*, 2020, 7(2), 251–267, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcde/qwaa021>
8. Waqas, H.; Farooq, U.; Alshehri, H.M.; Goodarzi, M. Marangoni-bioconvective flow of Reiner Philippoff nanofluid with melting phenomenon and nonuniform heat source/sink in the presence of a swimming microorganisms. *Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences*, 2021, 1–19, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mma.7727>
9. Sohail Ahmad , Muhammad Ashraf , Kashif Ali, Bioconvection due to gyrotactic microbes in a nanofluid flow through a porous medium, *Heliyon*, 2020, 6(12), 1-9, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05832>.
10. Aziz Ullah Awan , Syed Asif Ali Shah, Bagh Ali, Bio-convection effects on Williamson nanofluid flow with exponential heat source and motile microorganism over a stretching sheet, *Chinese Journal of physics*, June 2022, 77, Pages 2795-2810, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjph.2022.04.002>
11. Muhammad Jawad, Anwar Saeed , Muhammad Bilal, Taza Gul , Arshad Khan and Saleem Nasir, The impact of magnetohydrodynamic on bioconvection nanofluid flow with viscous dissipation and joule heating effect, *Engineering research express*, 2021, 3(1), 1-20, <https://doi.org/10.1088/2631-8695/abe7be>
12. B. Arun ,1 M. Deivanayaki ,2 and Selvakumar Kuppusamy Vaithilingam, Bioconvection flow in the presence of Casson nanoparticles on a stretching/shrinking vertical sheet with chemical reaction, *Journal of chemistry*, 2023, 2023, 1-9, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/6199200>
13. Gowda, R.J.P.; Kumar, R.N.; Jyothi, A.M.; Prasannakumara, B.C.; Sarris, I.E. Impact of binary chemical reaction and activation energy on heat and mass transfer of marangoni driven boundary layer flow of a non-Newtonian nanofluid. *Processes* 2021, 9(4), 1-18, <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9040702>.
14. Lund, L.A.; Omar, Z.; Khan, U.; Khan, I.; Baleanu, D.; Nisar, K.S. Stability analysis and dual solutions of micropolar nanofluid over the inclined stretching/shrinking surface with convective boundary condition, *Symmetry*, 2020, 12(1), 1-20, <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym12010074>
15. Muhammad Imran Asjad, Noman Sarwar, Bagh Ali, Sajjad Hussain, Thanin Sitthiwirattam and Jiraporn Reunsumrit, Impact of Bioconvection and Chemical Reaction on MHD Nanofluid Flow Due to exponential stretching sheet, *Symmetry*, 2021, 13(12), 1-16, 2334, <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym13122334>.
16. Damala Chenna Kesavaiah, Vellanki Nagaraju, Bhumarapu Venkateswarlu, Investigating the Influence of Chemical Reaction on MHD-Casson Nanofluid Flow via a Porous Stretching Sheet with Suction/Injection, 2022, 3(2), 47-62, <https://doi.org/10.54327/set2023/v3.i2.76>
17. Rashid Pourrajab and Aminreza Noghrehabadi, Bioconvection of Nanofluid Past Stretching Sheet in a Porous Medium in Presence of Gyrotactic Microorganisms with Newtonian Heating, *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 2018, 1-4, <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201822001004>.
18. G. Sandhya, K. Malleswari, G. Sarojamma, K. Sreelakshmi & P. V. Satya Narayana, Unsteady Casson nanofluid thin film flow over a stretching sheet with viscous dissipation and chemical reaction, *the European physical journal*, 2021, 230(5)1381-1390, <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjs/s11734-021-00033-z>.
19. Khalid Abdulkhalik M. Alharbi, Zeeshan Khan, Samina Zuhra, Saeed Islam, Aatif Ali, Elsayed Tag-Eldin and Samy Refahy Mahmoud, Numerical Study of the Electromagnetohydrodynamic Bioconvection Flow of Micropolar Nanofluid through a Stretching Sheet with Thermal Radiation and Stratification, *ACS Omega* 2022, 7, 42733–42751, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.2c04145>.
20. Pooja P. Humane, Vishwambar S. Patil, Amar B. Patil, Effects of radiation and chemical reaction on mhd Casson nanofluid flow past a porous stretching surface, *Computational thermal Sciences*, 2023, 15(5), 1-15, <https://doi.org/10.1615/ComputThermalScien.2023038739>.
21. Adnan Asghar, Liaquat Ali Lund, Zahir Shah, Narcisa Vrinceanu, Wejdan Deebani, and Meshal Shutaywi, Effect of Thermal Radiation on Three-Dimensional Magnetized Rotating Flow of a Hybrid Nanofluid, *Nanomaterials (Basel)*, 2022, 12(9), 1-16, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12091566>
22. Balla, C.S.; Ramesh, A.; Kishan, N.; Rashad, A.M.; Abdelrahman, Z.M.A. Bioconvection in oxytactic microorganism-saturated porous square enclosure with thermal radiation impact. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, 2020, 140(8), 2387–2395, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-019-09009-7>
23. Mohamad Nizam Othman, Alias Jedi and Nor Ashikin Abu Bakar, MHD Flow and Heat Transfer of Hybrid Nanofluid over an Exponentially Shrinking Surface with Heat Source/Sink, *Appl. Sci.* 2021, 11(17), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11178199>
24. Muhammad Jawad, Anwar Saeed, Muhammad Bilal , Taza Gul , Arshad Khan and Saleem Nasir, The impact of magnetohydrodynamic on bioconvection nanofluid flow with viscous dissipation and joule heating effects, *Engineering Research Express*, 2021, 3(1), 1-18, <https://doi.org/10.1088/2631-8695/abe7be>
25. Dharmendar Reddy Yanala, Shankar Goud Bejawada, Kottakkaran Sooppy Nisar, Influence of Chemical reaction and heat generation/absorption on Unsteady magneto Casson Nanofluid flow past a non-linear stretching Riga plate with radiation, *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, 2023, 50, 1-22, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2023.103494>.
26. N.S. Yousef, Ahmed M. Megahed, Nourhan I. Ghoneim, M. Elsafi, Eman Fares, Chemical reaction impact on MHD dissipative Casson-Williamson nanofluid flow over a slippery stretching sheet through porous medium, *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 2022 61(12), 10161–10170, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2022.03.032>

27. Ali. B.,Nie. Y, Khan. S. A., Sadiq M.T., Tariq M, Finite element simulation of multiple slip effects on MHD unsteady Maxwell nanofluid flow over a permeable stretching sheet with radiation and thermo-diffusion in the presence of chemical reaction, *Processes*, 2019, 7(9), 628. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr7090628>.
28. Syed Asif Ali Shah, N. Ameer Ahammad, ElSayed M. Tag El Din, Fehmi Gamaoun, Aziz Ullah Awan and Bagh Ali, Bio-Convection effects on Prandtl Hybrid nanofluid flow with chemical reaction and Motile microorganism over a stretching sheet, *nanomaterials*, 2022, 12(13), 1-19, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12132174>.